

Five Vital Factors Related to Employees' Job Performance

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Abstract—The purpose of this research was to study five vital factors related to employees' job performance. A total of 250 respondents were sampled from employees who worked at a public warehouse organization, Bangkok, Thailand. Samples were divided into two groups according to their work experience. The average working experience was about 9 years for group one and 28 years for group two. A questionnaire was utilized as a tool to collect data. Statistics utilized in this research included frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, t-test analysis, one way ANOVA, and Pearson Product-moment correlation coefficient. Data were analyzed by using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. The findings disclosed that the majority of respondents were female between 23-31 years old, single, and hold an undergraduate degree. The average income of respondents was less than 30,900 baht. The findings also revealed that the factors of organization chart awareness, job process and technology, internal environment, employee loyalty, and policy and management were ranked as medium level. The hypotheses testing revealed that difference in gender, age, and position had differences in terms of the awareness of organization chart, job process and technology, internal environment, employee loyalty, and policy and management in the same direction with low level.

Keywords—Employees, Factors Related, Job Performance, Public Warehouse Organization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Each organization has its own unique organizational behavior and ways of working together depend on its own unique environment such as tradition, culture, religion, valued and attitude. Some behavior has a positive and creative effect on the organization's survival and overall success, others may have a negative effect and hinder the success and drag the organization off track. The proper management can ameliorate employees' satisfaction and effectuate a motivation for employees dedicate to fulfill the goals of the organization. The evaluation of business management has contributed to many useful management techniques and therefore, the modern managers must be able to utilize these techniques to ameliorate the organization both in terms of efficiency and effectiveness [1].

The public warehouse organization is a legal entity which is designed to be a state enterprise, under the supervision of the ministry of commerce. It was designed to be able to function as effective as a private company. The purpose of founding the public warehouse organizations is do business mainly rice

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and other agricultural products in order to maintain good quality, low price, and sufficient supply for the needs of nation. By law, the organization is allowed to do price intervention whenever there is a market failure according to the policy set by ministry of commerce.

The public warehouse organization has been in business for over 50 years. There are over 500 fulltime employees. These employees can be divided into two groups: 1) Those who have been working with the organization for 30 years or more 2) Those who have been working with the organization for less than 10 years. These are two main groups of employees. The differences create a huge gap of the age, experience, position, and salary.

This research is aimed to study factors related to employees' job performance and it is hoped that the findings of this study can be used to enhance public warehouse organization's effectiveness.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. The Objectives of This Research

1. To compare employee's job performance according to their different demographic.
2. To study if there is a relationship of job performance and the awareness of these factors: organization chart, job process and technology, internal environment, employee loyalty, and policy and management

B. Research Hypotheses

Based on literature survey the following hypotheses have been derived:

1. Employees with different demographic background have different job performance.
2. There is a relationship of job performance and the awareness of these factors: organization chart, job process and technology, internal environment, employee loyalty, and policy and management.

C. Research Framework

Research framework for this study was drawn from papers, articles from researches and many theories. In addition, the framework of organization structure of Santiwong [2] and the theory of business environment Serirut [3] were utilized. The research framework stated that job performance is a function of both demographic variables and the awareness of organization chart, job process & technology, internal environment, employee loyalty, and policy & management.

Fig. 1 Conceptual framework

The population used in this study was all 530 operating employees and management employees. A total of 250 respondents were selected by using proportional stratified sampling and for each zone of the market. There were three stages in the process of selecting respondents.

Stage one: divide the population into two groups

- Group A: 458 Operating employees
- Group B: 72 Management employees

Stage two: quota sampling was used to get about 250 respondents from both groups

- Group A: 217 Operating employees
- Group B: 33 Management employees

Stage three: use systematic random sampling to collect respondent by distributing the questionnaire directly to each customers.

III. FINDINGS

The findings disclosed that the majority were female between 23-31 years old, married and live together. The majority had an undergraduate degree working for private companies. The average income of the respondents was less than 39,000 baht. The average work experience was about 9 years for the first group and 28 years for the second group. The findings also revealed the factors of organization chart awareness, job process and technology, internal environment, employee loyalty, and policy and management were ranked as medium level. The hypotheses testing revealed that different demographic factors of gender, age, and position had differences in terms of the awareness of organization chart, job process and technology, internal environment, employee

loyalty, and policy and management in the same direction with low level with the 0.05 level of significance.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. The findings revealed that employees with difference in age, gender, and position resulted in differences in job performance. This result concurred with the study of Tonpanprasert which studied the understanding of organization and job performance and found that employees with difference in gender had differences in job performance [4].
2. The findings revealed that the awareness of organization chart related to employees' job performance. A reason behind this finding may be that when the employees understand the organization, there becomes flexibility in work. Employees know their position and know who is important and who reports to whom. This agrees with Thai culture where people when know their proper place, tend work better and have high job satisfaction which may result in better job performance. This result concurred with the study of Tonsorn which reported that knowledge of organization chart helped employees to feel more comfortable in and around the organization and know their place and know who reports to whom [5].
3. The findings revealed that the awareness of job process and technology relate to employees' job performance. The reason for this may come from the fact that when employees know their job process and technology, it helps them to work faster with less stress. The result agreed with the study of Chanvanich, et al. which reported the findings from their study as the more employees understand their job process and technology, the better job performance they tend to have [6].
4. The findings revealed that the awareness of internal environment related to employees' job performance. This is because knowing the internal environment can help employees to adjust themselves to rules and regulation and the demand of workload from their organization. This result agreed with the study of Navikarn which reported the findings of his study as the more employees understand the internal environment, the better they can adjust themselves which results in a better job performance [7].
5. The findings revealed that the awareness of employee loyalty related to employees' job performance. This is because loyalty is one of the most important factors for employees to want to stay with the company in the long term. This result concurred with the study of Chanyou which explained that loyalty of employees mean they prefer to stay with the organization and are willing to work hard for the organization [8].
6. The findings revealed that the awareness of policy and management related to employees' job performance. This is because employees who know the policy will make a few mistakes and can adjust their ability and job

performance to meet the standard and the policy of the organization. This finding concurred with the study of Ronkaew which explained that the understanding of policy helps employees to understand the direction of the company and how to reach the goals [9].

V.SUGGESTIONS

1. The finding revealed that there were two distinguishable age groups. Therefore, knowledge transfer should be facilitated from experience group to less experience group in form of activities, teamwork, and seminar. This is important to keep implicit knowledge within the organization.
2. The findings revealed that the awareness of organization chart related to employees' job performance but not in a very high level. The organization should have a plan to help employees understand more about the organization chart and the flow of work inside the organization.
3. The findings revealed that the awareness of process of work and technology related to employees' job performance but not in a very high level. There should be an investment in up to date technology and training for employees to be able to better use technology and equipment to enhance their job performance.
4. The findings revealed that the awareness of customer loyalty related to employees' job performance but not in a very high level. The organization needs to create activities that allow employees to know each other and tries to reduce job dissatisfactions. Encourage employees to be more loyal and reward their loyalty.
5. The findings revealed that the awareness of policy and management related to employees' job performance but not in a very high level. The organization should get employees in every level to participate in the policy process and allow them to share their ideas to solve organization's problems.

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